

ASSESSING THE PROMISES AND PITFALLS OF SOCIAL MEDIA USAGE AMONG TEENAGERS IN LOKOJA

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ABSTRACT

The ubiquity of information and communication technology in this digital age has allowed for accessibility of digital media by both adults and even teenagers and children in many countries of the world, including Nigeria. The usage of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) through which teenagers access social media presents both promises and pitfalls which have implications on their development. Previous studies in Nigeria have shown that teenagers use social media for a number of purposes and are affected by it. However, using a qualitative method from a sample of teenagers of 14 to 17 years old in Lokoja Kogi state, this study sought to assess how teenagers have benefitted from social media and what risks they have encountered on social media. The study reveals that social media has been beneficial to teenagers in vocational skill acquisition and academic endeavour. On the other hand, teenagers have been exposed to online scam, receiving inappropriate requests from strangers online and pornographic content. The study recommends more social media education and mediation by parents and guardians.

Keywords: social media, teenagers, risks, benefits, experiences

Introduction

Advancement in technology from the mid-20th century has ushered us into an era of human civilization characterized by widespread access to information through the use of digital technology. This has been termed as the information age, computer age or digital age (Tucci, 2014). The ubiquitous nature of the media in this information age makes the internet, digital media and its contents accessible to both old and young people such that nowadays, even children and teenagers have access to a wide range of digital devices and contents both at home and in school (Adigwe, 2021).

Children and teenagers in the information age are referred to as digital natives who were born in the age of the internet; they have little or no experience of life prior to the use of the internet and they spend a lot of time on technological gadgets (Torocsik, Szucs & Khel, 2014). According to Amobi (2015) in Amobi, Sunday and Obia (2020 p.19), 'in times past, people saw the world through the eyes of parents, the textbooks and newspapers they were given to read, the radio programmes they were allowed to listen to and the television programme they were allowed to watch, but in today's digitised age, when children begin to ask google and Wikipedia questions from an early age, it has caused parents to lose some control of what they know, when and how they know it'.

A three-year study of teenagers from 13 to 18 years of age in South-east and North Central Nigeria showed that almost 60% of them had internet-enabled phones, mostly bought by their parents, guardians or

older siblings and about 31% of them used their personal money to purchase airtime and data bundle to browse the internet (Uzuegbunam, 2020).

The accessibility to information and communication technology such as social media has its benefits such as providing communication platforms, as an education resource, expanding worldviews and improving social skills, etc., and it also has risks for young, impressionable and inexperienced teenagers with low level of digital and social media literacy. They are vulnerable to being victims of online risks (Etumnu & Williams-Etumnu, 2023).

Researchers have suggested that qualitative and quantitative studies in data gathering and interpretation should be carried out to get the views of teenagers in Nigeria on risky experiences on digital media (James & Kur 2020; Kur, Kolo, & Iorpagher, 2019). Several studies have investigated the usage of social media by teenagers in Nigeria such as Oyovwe-Tinuoye and Adomi (2021), Ismail (2021), Odofin and Igabari (2023) and have shown that teenagers in Nigeria have been exposed to a number of risks online. However, most of these studies have been done quantitatively.

Qualitative studies regarding the experiences teenagers in Nigeria have had in relation to risky situations encountered as well as benefits derived is necessary to provide rich insight into their experiences on social media. Using a qualitative method, this study seeks to fill the gap in literature by investigating the experiences of teenagers on social media with a view of finding out the benefits they have derived and the risks they have encountered online.

Research Objectives

1. To find out the benefits teenagers in Lokoja derive from social media usage.
2. To find out the risks teenagers in Lokoja have encountered on social media.

Literature Review

Kaplan and Haenlein (2010) in Wolf, Sims and Yang (2018) defined social media as a collection of web-based programmes that support the production and sharing of user generated content and are based on the conceptual and technical underpinnings of web 2.0. All social media, whether fixed or mobile, use some sort of digital platform whereas, not every digital content is inevitably social media. Social media platforms includes Facebook, Whatsapp, Twitter, Tiktok, Instagram.

The social media ecosystem is always evolving, particularly among teenagers who are frequently at the forefront of this market. The minimum age requirement for ownership of accounts on some of the social media platforms such as Twitter, Instagram, Facebook, Snapchat, YouTube and WhatsApp as stated in their account policy is 13 years of age (Comms Week, 2017). This minimum age limit has also come under criticism as being problematic. In a report by Canales (2014), the Children's Online Privacy Protection Act of the United States prevent online platforms from collecting personal data from anyone under the age of 13 without parental approval.

However, most online service platforms instead chose to select 13 years of age as the age restriction to ownership on their platforms in order to reach the lucrative under-16 age market whereas, this age can be traced back to a 1990 law in the United States that prohibited tracking and collection of data from children. Some experts have called for the industry to support the move to raise the age limit in this modern times while some have said that the age limit will not really matter in keeping children safe as children will be exposed to the internet notwithstanding rules (Canales, 2014).

Social media has been a means for people to socialize and communicate with friends, an avenue for entertainment, information seeking, for self-presentation and expression. For example, a pew research centre survey of teens in the United States showed that eight out of ten teenagers think that social media helps them feel more connected to what is happening in their friends' life, it gives them a platform to express their creativity and it give them the impression that they have people who can support them during difficult times (Anderson, Vogels, Perrin & Raine, 2022; Nsude et al., 2023).

Ashiekpe and Mojaye (2017) affirmed that social media usage has become a daily activity for majority of Nigerian adolescents and youths who are actively involved in content generation as well as content consumption. Their pattern of use revolves around entertainment, identity expression, information and networking, and this affects their social development positively and negatively (Ashiekpe&Mojaye, 2017).

In Nigeria, a poll based on statistics from parental control modules by Kapersky Lab, which is an international cyber security firm revealed that when they are online, Nigerian youngsters (children and teens) spend more time on internet-connected social media platforms (35%) including Facebook, Google Mail, Twitter, WhatsApp, and Instagram and 27% spent time searching on video content, movies and music on Youtube (Ogunfuwa, 2018).

Tiktok is one of the most popular social media among teenagers where many teenagers create various viral content, participate in challenges and gain followers. With 55% of parents saying their child spends too much time on the phone or does nothing beneficial, a child's digital life can also be the source of family disputes (Asika, 2020).

In Nigeria, it is not uncommon to find that parents do not allow their teenage children to own phones or have social media accounts while they are in secondary school. In a report by News Agency of Nigeria (2022), parents expressed mixed perspectives on the appropriate age they allow their teenage children to start using phones. While some advocated for 14 years of age, others said 18 years is most preferred.

Some expressed worry that early usage of phones can lead to addiction and exposure to pornographic content. Some said even if teenagers are given phones, it should be cell phones which cannot access the internet. Most at times, if these teenagers need to use phones for any reason, they use their parent's phones or their sibling phones. However, some teenage children may access smartphones owned by their peers without their parents' knowledge.

Adomi, Oyovwe-Tinuoye and Igwela (2020) examined parents' awareness and monitoring of teenage children's use of social media in Delta state Nigeria. The result of their study showed that all the parents were aware of their teenagers' social media use, they used their mother's phone mostly, to access social media and facebook was the social media app that parents were mostly aware of.

Parents indicated that their teens use social media mostly during the day but they were mostly unaware of the amount of time spent on social media, they were aware of their use of social media for academic purposes. Parents indicated several ways they monitor their teens activities but monitoring their teen's chats on social media was the most used. Concerning parental awareness of influence of social media on teens, parents mostly indicated positive influences rather than negatives.

Another study by Ismail (2021) examined the impact of social media on teenagers between the ages of 13 to 19 in Abuja, based on the uses and gratification theory. Using survey method, the study found that social media has both positive and negative impact on teenagers. Teenagers in Nigeria are motivated to use social media mostly to create and maintain friendships, to get news, to watch videos and view pictures, play games and for academic research.

The negative impact includes cyberbullying, being lured into social vices, and being influenced to change themselves physically to conform to role models they see online. Overall, these studies employ quantitative method to examine the influences social media has on teenagers.

Theoretical Framework

This study is based on the Uses and Gratification theory credited to Jay Blumler and Elihu Katz in 1974. The theory assumes that media users are active audience who exercise control over their media consumption and that people use the media to gratify specific needs and wants. Theory of uses and gratification treats the audience as active, logical, resistant to persuasion, and making decisions based on their desires (Erzurum, 2022; Agbim et al., 2023).

It views the use of communication technologies as a process of need satisfaction. The fact that new media technologies allow users to participate actively rather than passively is one of its most significant advantages. One of the most crucial ideas about the uses and gratification theory is the idea of an active audience.

This theory is relevant to one of the objectives of this study which is to investigate the benefits of social media usage by teenagers, in the sense that teenagers use social media platforms based on the needs and wants it satisfies for them and the benefits they derive from its usage.

Methodology

This study adopts a qualitative research approach. According to Creswell (2014), the focus of qualitative research is examining and comprehending the meaning that an individual or group of individuals assigns to a social or human situation. Since the study sought to determine the risky online experiences teenagers have had on social media this study finds using qualitative methods suitable because it provides the researcher the opportunity to understand the concepts from the perspectives and lived experiences of the respondents in order to provide adequate answers to the research questions.

The research method used in the study is in-depth interview method which is a qualitative method. The population of the study includes teenage children in Lokoja. Teenagers who use social media were purposively selected because they are in the best position to give their views on the benefits and risks of social media based on their experience. Teenagers used in the study are limited to those who are between 14 to 17 years of age because they are thought to be old enough and suitable to provide answers to the research questions asked. The study setting is Lokoja, the Kogi State capital.

In determining the sample size sufficient to reach saturation, Bernard (2013) asserts that there is growing consensus that 10 to 20 core research participants are sufficient to identify and comprehend the central problems in any study of lived experience. The sample size eventually used in this study consisted of 12 teenagers.

Respondents were gotten via snowballing i.e. one respondent recommends another respondent. The researcher met with most of the teenagers at their homes while some interviews were conducted online as well, after the parent of the teenagers gave permission for their wards to participate. Interviews usually lasted for 30 minutes, and were conducted between November to February, 2024. Interviews were recorded and transcribed for deductive thematic analysis.

Presentation of Data and Discussion of Findings

S/N	Informant	Code Name	Age	Gender
1	Informant 1	Inf. T1	16	Female
2	Informant 2	Inf. T2	15	Female
3	Informant 3	Inf. T3	16	Male
4	Informant 4	Inf. T4	17	Female
5	Informant 5	Inf. T5	16	Male
6	Informant 6	Inf. T6	15	Male
7	Informant 7	Inf. T7	17	Female
8	Informant 8	Inf. T8	16	Male
9	Informant 9	Inf. T9	15	Male
10	Informant 10	Inf. T10	14	Female
11	Informant 11	Inf. T11	17	Female
12	Informant 12	Inf. T12	16	Male

Source: 2024 Field Data Collection

Theme 1: Benefits of Social Media Usage by teenagers

The benefits of social media in this study are the advantages the teenagers derive from the social media platforms they interact with. Two major subthemes were drawn from their responses to this research question.

Sub Theme 1: Academic Benefit

Social media applications are used for a variety of purposes. Teenagers in this study are found to be either in senior secondary school students (SS2 to SS3), those who are through with secondary school awaiting admission into higher institution, or those who just gained admission into higher institutions.

Thus, many of them asserted to using social media for purposes that has to do with academics and school activities. Inf. T6 said ‘I use the social media app especially whatsapp every day to get update on my school activities’. Similarly, Inf. T1 opined that, ‘I use it for research for my school assignments, participate in group chats in school for information about lectures, to chat and stuff’.

On her part, Inf. T10 stated this: ‘I access social media through my personal phone. I use Facebook, Instagram and Tiktok. I watch short videos on Tiktok. The main reason I was given phone was for research and homework, check youtube videos because I am a science student. I started using it in ss1 but with my parents’ phone and then I got my personal phone when I was in ss2. I use it when we have assignments and when I am bored. (Inf.10).

Also, Inf. T7 noted that ‘I use Snapchat because it's an interesting app and of course my Snapchat AI... that dude knows almost everything, it helps me with my assignment and school research that's why I use Snapchat’ (Inf. T7).

Their responses show that teenagers find social media very useful to get information for assignments in school, participate in group chats to keep themselves updated on lecture schedule. Their response also shows this purpose is one of the reasons their parents allow them have their personal phones.

Sub Theme 2: Vocational Skill

Teenage respondents opined that social media is beneficial as a platform that exposes them to learn vocational skills and to promote their business endeavours through showcasing their handiwork online for patronage. In recent times, teenagers and youths are usually encouraged to learn one skill or the other so that they can be self-employed and earn some income.

It is not uncommon to find teenagers being apprentices learning one skill or the other such as fashion design, hair dressing, catering and the likes. According to the respondents, social media has become a veritable tool to gain additional knowledge in such vocational skills as one could easily find content or communities involved in those vocations where they share ideas and new developments.

While supporting this claim, Inf. T10 stated thus: ‘Social media is beneficial in some way. There are some students who use social media to do business and get a small income. I also explore these apps on things like fashion designing and bead making because I am learning those skills. I use social media to watch videos about it and learn more. My mum advertises my works on whatsapp. My brother is into crafts, and he uses social media to search for crafts on facebook and youtube. So, it is good for business’ (Inf. T10).

Theme 2: Risky Online Experiences among Lokoja teenagers

Social media platforms are virtual spaces that interconnect people of various countries, tribes, color, and personality from all walks of life. Thus, the good, bad and ugly can be found on social media. Teenagers who are young and impressionable when they find themselves in this virtual space are exposed to these good, bad and ugly sides in the social media environment. At times, as findings in this study shows, they find themselves in risky situations. Risky online experience in this study refers to being in any situation during interactions in the digital media space, which can cause harm to the teenagers in one way or the other.

While responding to the inquiry on the risky online experiences that teenagers in Lokoja have had on social media, few of the teenagers expressed that they rarely experience risky situations online. They attributed this to the fact that they register and use just one or two social media accounts and some of those social media apps are more private, consisting of only their friends and families and so they rarely come across risky situations such as meeting strangers online.

In the words of Inf. T9, “I have not really experienced anything that put me at risk. I use whatsapp mostly and it’s more private. People I have on my contact are my close friends and family so I hardly encounter strangers or the likes”. However, other informants identified exposure to online scam, exposure to inappropriate content, meeting strangers, receiving inappropriate requests from strangers as some of risky experiences encountered on the social media.

Sub-Theme 1: Online Scam

Social media is like a market place where people buy and sell ideas, goods and services in a virtual environment. While one can view and patronise variety of goods and services, users are also wary of advertisers that are not really who they claim to be. From enticing offers of return on investment that look too good to be true, to deceptive or false identities of advertisers trying to sell one thing or the other, various forms of scams exist on social media and many users have been victims, losing their money or having their information compromised. In this study, online scam refers to the use of the social media by people referred to as scammers who deceive or trick people into giving away their money or valuables.

The data gathered in this study shows that teenagers are not left out of being exposed to and at times, being victims of scams online. Some of the informants in this study said they were exposed to different online scam and shared their experiences. For instance, Inf. T10 said: 'I came online on whatsapp one day and saw that I had been added to a group where they were saying we should pay a certain amount of money to get something in return. I have heard of online scamming from my parents before that encounter. So, I didn't need to inform my parents about it. I just left the group because it is risky to just pay money for just anything online' (Inf. T10).

Coming from another brand of internet scam, Inf. T8 said: 'I encountered someone on facebook who told me he could show me how to make money in 30 days. He was a ritualist. He sent me pictures of his shrine, showed me pictures of money, and said if I wanted to make money, I should chat with him' (Inf. T8). 'It was on whatsapp. I don't know who added me up but I just saw that I was added to a group 'legit update'. I fell into their trap. The group was about crypto and hacking. They asked us to pay money to learn how to make money. I thought it would work because you know now, sometimes there are financial family issues. I paid 6k, which I never got back' (Inf. T12).

From the responses of teenagers in this study, while one fell victim to scam, others were proactive and cautious because of prior knowledge of online scams which they had gotten from their parents or people around them, which made them ignore such offers, ask the right questions or block the senders. Some also stated their parents had taught them to avoid making money through illegal means. As Inf. T8 said 'I ignored the ritualist because my mother has taught me what people like that do is not good, it is wrong to use ritual to make money.

Their response also shows that facebook and whatsapp were the social media apps in which they came in contact with these scammers and the means was by being added to unfamiliar group chats by strangers and receiving direct messages from the strangers.

Sub-Theme 2: Pornographic Content

Pornographic content involves sexually explicit messages especially videos and images which can be found on social media that can cause sexual arousal. Generally, the Nigerian society frowns at youths being exposed to or viewing pornography as it is against acceptable morals and value, more so for teenagers who are young and impressionable.

Parents in this study expressed disapproval and disgust for sexual materials and nudity on social media. Pornographic content in form of text, images and videos exist on social media and while some users search for such content, at times unsolicited pornographic content pop up while navigating the social media environment, as the informants in this study have mentioned.

Meanwhile, while responding to the question on the risky online experiences that teenagers in Lokoja have come across on social media, the informants mentioned exposure to unsolicited pornographic content. For instance, Inf. T1 stated that 'Yes, I can be scrolling down on a social media site (facebook) and

come across pornographic content. I usually just scroll past it'. Also, Inf. T2, affirmed 'at times I see links to some videos with some sexual description on facebook, some in accounts of people that have been hacked'.

Sub-Theme 3: Inappropriate Requests from Strangers

As social media connects the world together on a virtual space, it is not uncommon for users to meet new people and connect with strangers for valuable purposes. However, reports from teenagers in this study showed that strangers may not always come with good intentions as some make requests from them that are sexually inappropriate. The shared the following experiences.

Inf. T1 said 'I have also received friend requests from white people I don't know. They requested for my pictures. And I tell them I don't send my pictures to strangers'. 'When I started using facebook, I met a foreigner from SA who started chatting with me, a guy, telling me he has feelings for me. I was like bro I'm 15 and wait you're also a bro so what are you talking about? (laughs). He said so? Love is not about gender. On hearing that, I blocked the gay bastard immediately. That was the first and last time' (Inf. T6).

On her part, the Inf. T7 stated thus: 'One day, a boy texted me, and the first thing he said was, Let's sex chat. When I opened the message, I didn't know what he meant by sex chat, so I took it upon myself to search for the meaning of the word. I then proceeded to text my friends about it. Then, the same boy texted me and asked why I left. I read his message and didn't reply. Then I asked, what was I supposed to reply? I asked where he was chatting from because I wanted to know if that's how they act from his place, of which he said Iran. To my surprise, he also said he was 18. But I think I handled the case well because he left me and didn't bother me anymore' (Inf. T7).

Similarly, a sixteen-year-old Inf. T5 mentioned that 'I have deleted my Snapchat account twice this year because some people keep messaging me and asking me for things that are not holy (nude pictures)' (Inf. T5).

These responses show that both male and female teenagers are prone to receiving inappropriate requests such as requesting for nude pictures and sexual messages. The social media platforms where they have come in contact with such in this study are facebook and snapchat.

Discussion of Findings

This study found that teenagers find social media beneficial to them because it is a tool for them to get useful information for their academic endeavour and for their vocational skill acquisition. This is in line with Sumadevi (2023) that social media platforms offer an abundance of educational resources and information, giving young people access to a wide range of viewpoints and knowledge.

This is also in line with Oyovwe-Tinuoye and Adomi (2021) which revealed that the most common reasons teens use social media is for academic matters with associates, entertainment and to browse current news. Similarly, Ito et al. (2019) noted that online communities for common interests, pastimes, or identities can also be significant for teenagers. For a variety of activities, such as reading, music, crafts and the creative arts, and games, affinity networks can offer guidance and support.

Risks associated with adolescents' media use categorised by Livingstone, Kirwil, Ponte and Staksrud (2014) into four areas including conduct risk (e.g., bullying, sexting, misuse of personal information), contact risk (e.g. meeting strangers online, experiencing stalking, harassment), content risk (e.g., being exposed to deceptive content, pornography, violent content, inappropriate content) and commercial risk (e.g., online purchase scam, negative advertising, etc.). The teenagers in this study revealed

that they have been exposed to pornographic content, meeting and receiving inappropriate requests from strangers, and online. Therefore, this is consistent with Livingstone et al. (2014) finding on contact risk, content risk and commercial risk of being exposed to online scam. However, teenagers in this study did not report being involved in any conduct risk.

The subthemes generated from the study includes meeting strangers online, receiving inappropriate requests from strangers online and online scam. Opesade and Adetona (2021) finding revealed that exposure to provocative content and cyberbullying involving being excluded from group or activity and seeing unpleasant content or remarks about them being shared by others are the most predominant cyber risk experienced by students in Ibadan. This is in contrast with the finding of this study. Though most of the respondents know about cyberbullying, they report that they have not been victims of cyberbullying.

Moreso, Opesade and Adetona's(2021) study revealed that seeing photos or videos of nudity online is the most common risk or sexual solicitation experienced by secondary students, followed by exposure to sexual messages posted online, and request to have conversation regarding sexual actions online. This is in consonance with the findings of this study as the teenage respondents have affirmed that their risky experience include exposure to inappropriate content such as nudity and receiving inappropriate (sexual) requests from strangers online. However, in contrast with the findings of Opesade and Adetona (2021), another contact risk that this study has revealed is contact with scammers online.

Noori, Sayes, and Anwari (2023) noted that young students are the victims of social media more than anybody else. Thus, it is not out of place to see that young teenagers are vulnerable to being victims of deceptive people online such as scammers. This is in consonance with Livingstone et al. (2014) who found that contact risk usually from adults including possibility of inappropriate contact with people, inappropriate sexual contact with pedophiles, contact with people with fake identities, impersonation, face-to-face meetings after contact with strangers online, etc. are one of the major issues that bothers teens online.

Compared to other groups, those under the age of 20 have had the highest percentage in money lost to scammers in the past five years (Fletcher, 2023). Young people fall victim of scam because they rush into offers they see on social media without thinking, being impulsive. Due to the borderless nature of the internet, scammers can operate from anywhere in the world, deceiving people in giving their money or sensitive information away. As Akewushola (2023) noted, according to reports, West African countries especially Nigeria, Southeast Asia and Eastern Europe are known to have a high rate of online scam activities.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The study qualitatively investigated the benefits derived and risks encountered by teenagers on social media to gain rich insight into the experiences of teenagers. The study concludes that social media usage by teenagers is beneficial to them and also exposes them to risks that they may be vulnerable to.

This shows that teenagers have to be guided when they begin to access social media platforms and own personal accounts in the digital media environment. Social media can be harnessed to help teenagers improve their vocational skills and their educational pursuit. This study therefore recommends parental mediation whereby parents interact with their wards on how to navigate the digital media environment and maximize the opportunities therein while avoiding the risks.

In order to efficiently guide teenagers, parents therefore have to be knowledgeable about the digital media environment as well. Older siblings of teenagers and other family members around teenagers who are more knowledgeable and social media literate also have the duty to guide teenagers and monitor their social media usage to ensure responsible usage.

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